

To customers with steel supplies for construction projects with LEED certification

Manufacturer declaration for building projects with LEED certification (Data 2023)

Manufacturer	Stahl Gerlafingen AG Bahnhofstrasse CH-4563 Gerlafingen
Production site	Bahnhofstrasse CH-4563 Gerlafingen
Products	Rebar (coils, bars, meshes) + profiles
Production route	Electric arc furnace with use of 100% steel scrap
Iron content:	97-98% Fe
Origin of the steel scrap	63% Switzerland, 37% import near the border (D/F/A) Average transport distance about 150km (rail, truck, ship) No transport > 800km About 91 % post-consumer scrap About 9 % pre-consumer scrap
Recycling paths of the recycling materials produced in the production process	Slag: recycling gravel (brand name RUVIDO) Steel mill dust: zinc and lead recycling Scales: steel or cement production
Relevant standards	<u>Rebar:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SIA 262 - DIN 488-2 until -4 - NFA 35-080-1 / -2 - NEN 6008 - NBN A24-301 / -302 + PTV 310 <u>Profiles:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EN 10025-1 / -2 <u>Management System:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO 9001 / 14001 / 45001

Stahl Gerlafingen AG

Alain Creteur

CEO

Gerlafingen, March 2024

Gianluca Rossi

Energy management and Sustainability